

DAMAGE PROGRESSION ANALYSIS OF SELF-HEALING POLYMER COMPOSITES CONTAINING MICROCAPSULES

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ABSTRACT

Three-dimensional finite element analysis was performed using a representative volume element (RVE) model to predict damage progression behavior of spread carbon fiber (SCF)/epoxy (EP) laminates containing microcapsules. Two RVE models with different dispersion state of microcapsules were constructed. The well-dispersion model considers well distributed microcapsules in the SCF/EP laminates and the aggregation model presents aggregation of microcapsules in the interlayer of the SCF/EP laminates. The results indicated that the damage progression behavior of SCF/EP laminates containing microcapsules are influenced by the dispersion state of microcapsules.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRPs) are attractive because they provide advantageous mechanical properties such as high specific stiffness and strength. Therefore, these materials have been used in many structural materials such as airplanes and cars. However, complexity is present in these materials and causes microscopic damages under mechanical and thermal loadings in service. These damages are very difficult to detect and repair because they can form deep within the materials. Recently, a concept of self-healing was proposed. Self-healing materials are designed to repair damage automatically, thereby improving the durability and reliability of materials.

A self-healing polymer was developed by White et al. [1]. The microencapsulated dicyclopentadiene (DCPD) monomer was dispersed in an epoxy together with Grubbs' catalysts. When damages occur in the epoxy composite, cracks propagate and rupture the embedded microcapsules. The released DCPD monomer contacts the Grubbs' catalysts, a polymerization of DCPD monomer is taken place and the cracked faces can be bonded.

Kessler et al. [2] used the self-healing polymer as the matrix of a woven glass fiber/epoxy laminates and showed the recovery of interlaminar fracture toughness. Yin et al. [3] proposed a woven glass fiber/epoxy laminates with a microencapsulated epoxy healing agent and latent curing agent. Patel et al. [4] was performed compression after impact testing to investigate recovery of residual compressive strength in woven glass fiber/epoxy laminates containing microencapsulated DCPD monomer. Yuan et al. [5] embedded a microencapsulated epoxy healing agent and its curing agent within a woven glass fiber/epoxy laminates and assessed healing efficiency of compressive properties.

Sanada et al. [6-8] successfully demonstrated the repair of interfacial debonding to unidirectional CFRPs by using fiber strands coated with the above self-healing polymer. They also examined an interlaminar shear strength and a healing efficiency of spread carbon fiber (SCF)/epoxy (EP) laminates using the self-healing polymer as the matrix [9, 10]. Figure 1 shows the self-healing system of self-healing SCF/EP laminates. Many researchers have described that the use of SCF leads to improvement in damage resistance properties of the CFRP laminates [11, 12]. Therefore, an initial properties of the laminates can be improved by using SCFs. The aggregation of microcapsules can also be prevented by using SCFs, thereby increasing the strength recovery of the laminates. However, the experimental results showed that as the microcapsule concentration increased, the healing efficiency increased and the apparent interlaminar shear strength decreased.

Previously, finite element analysis of the SCF/EP laminates containing microcapsules was performed [13]. By using Digimat-FE software, the representative volume element (RVE) models were generated and solved to evaluate the elastic properties of the laminates. The analytical results showed that the elastic properties of the SCF/EP laminates containing microcapsules is influenced by the dispersion state of microcapsules.

The purpose of this study is to investigate damage progression behavior in SCF/EP laminates containing microcapsules. A three dimensional RVE model was used to study the mechanical response of the damaged laminates. The failure criteria are incorporated into the RVE model to study the damage distributions within the laminates.

Figure 1: Self-healing system of self-healing SCF/EP laminates.

2 MATERIAL PROPERTIES

Table 1 shows Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of materials used in this study. The materials were modeled as linear elastic and isotropic materials. In an actual microcapsules consisting DCPD core and urea-formaldehyde (UF) polymeric shell, UF shell is very thin. Therefore, the core-shell microcapsules were homogenized as a spherical isotropic inclusion having negligible Young's modulus and incompressible. Moreover, the interface of those were assumed to be perfectly bonded.

Table 1: Material properties used in this study.

Material	Microcapsule	SCF [14]	Epoxy [15]
Young's modulus (GPa)	10^{-6}	230	3.4
Poisson's ratio	0.49	0.2	0.3

3 MODEL DESCRIPTION

The three dimensional periodic RVE model was generated by using Digimat-FE software (MSC software). We investigated two cases for RVE models with well-dispersed and aggregated microcapsules. A rectangular cartesian coordinate system (x, y, z) is used. The RVE size was taken to be $0.5 \text{ mm} \times 0.5 \text{ mm} \times 0.3 \text{ mm}$. The microcapsule and SCF volume fraction, V_f^C and V_f^{SCF} , were determined by following equations, respectively:

$$V_f^C = \frac{V^C}{V^{\text{SCF}} + V^{\text{M}} + V^C} \quad (1)$$

$$V_f^{\text{SCF}} = \frac{V^{\text{SCF}}}{V^{\text{SCF}} + V^{\text{M}} + V^C} \quad (2)$$

where V^{SCF} , V^{M} and V^C are the respective volumes of the SCF, matrix and microcapsules. The microcapsule and SCF volume fraction were set to be 23.1 and 12.4 vol%, respectively. The microcapsule diameter, d , was set to be 113 μm .

3.1 Well-Dispersion Model

Figure 2 shows the schematic image of well-dispersion model of SCF/EP laminates containing microcapsules. The RVE model contained the homogenized SCF/EP composites and the homogenized microcapsules. The SCF/EP composites in well-dispersion model were modeled as a homogeneous, elastic and transversely isotropic material with properties as shown in Table 2. E_x and E_y are the Young's moduli, G_{xy} is the shear modulus, ν_{xy} and ν_{yz} are the Poisson's ratio, and the subscripts x , y and z are related to the three axes of the coordinate system. The Poisson's ratio ν_{xy} (ν_{yz} , ν_{xz}) reflects shrinkage (expansion) in the y (z , z)-direction due to tensile (compressive) stress in the x (y , x)-direction. These properties were calculated with the cubic RVE model containing the continuous SCFs with diameter of 7 μm and fiber orientation along x -direction.

Figure 2: Schematic image of well-dispersion model (dimensions in mm).

Table 2: Material properties of the homogenized SCF/EP composites in well-dispersion model.

Young's modulus (GPa)		Shear modulus (GPa)	Poisson's ration	
E_x	E_y	G_{xy}	ν_{xy}	ν_{yz}
39.4	4.79	1.81	0.279	0.398

3.2 Aggregation Model

To consider aggregation of microcapsules in the interlayer of the SCF/EP laminates, two layers were constructed: microcapsule/EP and SCF/EP composite layers as shown in Figure 3. From experimental results, the thickness of microcapsule/EP and SCF/EP composite layers were set to be 0.195 and 0.105 mm, respectively. The SCF/EP composites in aggregation models were also assumed to be a homogeneous, elastic and transversely isotropic materials. Table 3 shows these properties of the homogenized SCF/EP composites in aggregation models.

Figure 3: Schematic image of aggregation model (dimensions in mm).

Table 3: Material properties of the homogenized SCF/EP composites in aggregation model.

Young's modulus (GPa)		Shear modulus (GPa)	Poisson's ration	
E_x	E_y	G_{xy}	ν_{xy}	ν_{yz}
81.7	6.93	2.75	0.256	0.376

4 DAMAGE PROGRESSION ANALYSIS

4.1 Strength Prediction of SCF/EP Composites

The strengths of SCF/EP composites were evaluated. The maximum stress criterion was used to predict failure of the SCF.

$$\sigma_{xx} = \begin{cases} F_{xt} & \text{when } \sigma_{xx} > 0 \\ -F_{xc} & \text{when } \sigma_{xx} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (3a)$$

$$\sigma_{zz} = \begin{cases} F_{zt} & \text{when } \sigma_{zz} > 0 \\ -F_{zc} & \text{when } \sigma_{zz} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (3b)$$

$$|\tau_{zx}| = F_{zx} \quad (3c)$$

where σ_{xx} , σ_{yy} , σ_{zz} , τ_{yz} , τ_{zx} and τ_{xy} are the stress components, F_{xt} , F_{yt} , F_{zt} , F_{xc} , F_{yc} , F_{zc} , F_{yz} , F_{zx} and F_{xy} are the three uniaxial tensile strengths, the three uniaxial compressive strengths and the three shear strengths, respectively and the subscripts x , y and z are related to the three axes of the coordinate system. The tensile and compressive strengths of SCF are set to be 3100 MPa [14]. The von Mises criterion was also used to evaluate failure in the epoxy matrix.

$$(\sigma_{yy} - \sigma_{zz})^2 + (\sigma_{zz} - \sigma_{xx})^2 + (\sigma_{xx} - \sigma_{yy})^2 + 6(\tau_{yz}^2 + \tau_{zx}^2 + \tau_{xy}^2) = 2\sigma_T^2 \quad (4)$$

where σ_T is the tensile strength of epoxy matrix and set to be 70 MPa [8]. If the elements satisfied the criteria, the material would damage. When the failure occurred, the stiffness of the elements was reduced by one-hundredth.

4.2 Damage Progression Prediction of SCF/EP Laminates Containing Microcapsules

The damage progression behavior of the homogenized SCF/EP composites in SCF/EP laminates containing microcapsules was predicted using Tsai-Wu criterion.

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\sigma_{xx}^2}{F_{xt}F_{xc}} + \frac{\sigma_{yy}^2 + \sigma_{zz}^2}{F_{yt}F_{yc}} + \frac{\tau_{xy}^2 + \tau_{zx}^2}{F_{xy}^2} + \frac{4\tau_{yz}^2}{F_{yt}F_{yc}} - \frac{\sigma_{xx}\sigma_{yy} + \sigma_{xx}\sigma_{zz}}{2F_{xt}F_{xc}} \\ & - \frac{2\sigma_{yy}\sigma_{zz}}{F_{yt}F_{yc}} + \left(\frac{1}{F_{xt}} - \frac{1}{F_{xc}} \right) \sigma_{xx} + \left(\frac{1}{F_{yt}} - \frac{1}{F_{yc}} \right) (\sigma_{yy} + \sigma_{zz}) = 1 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The criterion considers a transversely isotropic material and assumes the material isotropy in the plane normal to x -axis and identical strengths in tension and compression for shear loadings. The strengths used in the criterion are presented in Table 4. These strengths were evaluated using damage progression analysis of the SCF/EP composites. The strengths, F_{xc} and F_{yc} , are assumed to be $0.753 F_{xt}$ and $4.34 F_{yt}$, respectively [14]. In the case of aggregation model, the von Mises criterion was also used to evaluate failure of the epoxy matrix in microcapsule/EP composite layer. If the elements satisfied the criteria, the stiffness of the elements was reduced by one-hundredth.

Table 4: Strengths of the homogenized SCF/EP composites.

Strengths (MPa)	Well-dispersion model	Aggregation model
F_{xt}	318	708
F_{xc}	239	533
F_{yt}	30.1	32.1
F_{yc}	131	139
F_{xy}	14.3	15.8

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 4 shows the effect of microcapsule dispersion state in the SCF/EP laminates containing microcapsules on the predicted stress-strain curve. The peak shear stress obtained from the aggregation model was slightly higher than that obtained from well-dispersion model. On the other hand, the initial slope of the predicted stress-strain curve (stiffness) obtained from well-dispersion model was increased as compared to that obtained from aggregation model.

Figure 5 shows predicted stress-strain curve and cross-sections of well-dispersion model of SCF/EP laminates containing microcapsules, and the red region indicates the damage. The points labeled A, B, C and D presents the correspondence between the strain and the damage. At the point A, the damage progression began near the microcapsules and the predicted stress-strain curve showed the peak shear stress of about 4.47 MPa. Then, the damage propagated through microcapsules.

The corresponding results for the aggregation model is shown Figure 6. Similar to the well-dispersion model, the damage of aggregation model generated near the microcapsules and the peak shear stress indicated about 4.95 MPa. But the damage progression in aggregation model is different from that in well-dispersion model, and the damage did not propagate through microcapsules. After the peak shear stress, the damage of the homogenized SCF/EP composites close to the layer interface also initiated and propagated. It is considered that the damage progression behavior of SCF/EP laminates containing microcapsules are influenced by the dispersion state of microcapsules.

Figure 4: Predicted stress-strain curve obtained from well-dispersion and aggregation models of SCF/EP laminates containing microcapsules.

Figure 5: Predicted stress-strain curve and damage progressions in well-dispersion model of SCF/EP laminates containing microcapsules.

Figure 6: Predicted stress-strain curve and damage progressions in aggregation model of SCF/EP laminates containing microcapsules.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The damage progression behavior of the SCF/EP laminates containing microcapsules were predicted, and the shear strength of the laminates was evaluated. The damage progressions in well-dispersion and aggregation models were different. Moreover, the shear strength obtained from aggregation model was slightly higher than that obtained from well-dispersion model. However, the stiffness of well-dispersion model was higher than that of aggregation model. Therefore, the damage progression behavior of SCF/EP laminates containing microcapsules were influenced by the dispersion state of microcapsules.

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REFERENCES

- [1] S.R. White, N.R. Sottos, P.H. Geubelle, J.S. Moore, M.R. Kessler, S.R. Sriram, E.N. Brown and S. Viswanathan, Autonomic healing of polymer composites, *Nature*, **409**, 2001, pp. 794-797.
- [2] M.R. Kessler, N.R. Sottos and S.R. White, Self-healing structural composite materials, *Composites: Part A*, **34**, 2003, pp. 743-753.
- [3] T. Yin, L. Zhou, M.Z. Rong and M.Q. Zhang, Self-healing woven glass fabric/epoxy composites with the healant consisting of micro-encapsulated epoxy and latent curing agent, *Smart Materials and Structures*, **17**, 2008, pp. 015019-015026.
- [4] A.J. Patel, N.R. Sottos, E.D. Wetzel and S.R. White, Autonomic healing of low-velocity impact damage in fiber-reinforced composites, *Composite: Part A*, **41**, 2010, pp. 360-368.
- [5] Y.C. Yuan, Y. Ye, M.Z. Rong, H. Chen, J. Wu, M.Q. Zhang, S.X. Qin and G.C. Yang, Self-healing of low-velocity impact damage in glass fabric/epoxy composites using an epoxy-mercaptan healing agent, *Smart Materials and Structures*, **20**, 2011, pp. 015024-015034.
- [6] K. Sanada, I. Yasuda and Y. Shindo, Transverse tensile strength of unidirectional fibre-reinforced polymers and self-healing of interfacial debonding, *Plastics, Rubber and Composites*, **35**, 2006, pp. 67-72.
- [7] K. Sanada, N. Itaya and Y. Shindo, Self-healing of interfacial debonding in fiber-reinforced polymers and effect of microstructure on strength recovery, *The Open Mechanical Engineering Journal*, **2**, 2008, pp. 97-103.
- [8] K. Sanada, Y. Mizuno and Y. Shindo, Damage progression and notched strength recovery of fiber-reinforced polymers encompassing self-healing of interfacial debonding, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **49**, 2015, pp. 1765-1776.
- [9] K. Sanada, T. Suyama and Y. Nassho, Interlaminar shear strength and self-healing of spread carbon fiber/epoxy laminates containing microcapsules, *Journal of the Society of Materials Science, Japan*, **66**, 2017, pp. 299-305.
- [10] Y. Nassho and K. Sanada, Self-healing and microstructure optimization of spread carbon fiber/epoxy laminates, *Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Self-Healing Materials, Friedrichshafen, Germany, June 25-28, 2017*.
- [11] T. Yokozeki, A. Kuroda, A. Yoshimura, T. Ogasawara and T. Aoki, Damage characterization in thin-ply composite laminates under out-of-plane transverse loadings, *Composite Structures*, **93**, 2010, pp. 49-57.
- [12] H. M. EL-Dessouky and C.A. Lawrence, Ultra-lightweight carbon fibre/thermoplastic composite material using spread tow technology, *Composites: Part B*, **50**, 2013, pp. 91-97.
- [13] Y. Nassho and K. Sanada, Finite element analysis of elastic properties of self-healing polymer composites containing microcapsules, *Proceedings of the 18th European Conference on Composite Materials, Athens, Greece, June 24-28, 2018*.
- [14] I.M. Daniel and O. Ishai, *Engineering mechanics of composite materials second edition*, Oxford University Press, 2006.
- [15] A. Ahmed, K. Sanada, M. Fanni and A.A. El-Moneim, A practical methodology for modeling and verification of self-healing microcapsules-based composites elasticity, *Composite Structures*, **184**, 2018, pp. 1092-1098.